

TAILORING OF MICROSTRUCTURE IN C/C-SiC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMC) have been developed via the Liquid Silicon Infiltration (LSI) process which allows the manufacturing of highly complex and integrated components of C/C-SiC. Compared to other CMC techniques this process shows a big potential for cost effective production of CMC components because of its simplicity in processing and the comparably low raw material costs. As for all other composite materials the fibre/matrix bonding has a dominating influence on the fracture behaviour and the thermal and mechanical properties. This paper deals with the interactions between the fibre/matrix bondings and the formation of the microstructure for tailored material design of C/C-SiC.

Keywords: Ceramic Matrix Composites, C/C-SiC, fibre/matrix bonding, LSI process, microstructure, pretreatment

INTRODUCTION

Originally, the DLR developed the LSI process for structural aerospace applications. Heat shields for reentry capsules and intake ramps for a hypersonic aircraft have been successfully realized as demonstrators. From the beginning of material's development emphasis was given to a simple and short production process to overcome the restrictions in costs and availability of traditional CMC techniques. Simplicity in processing has been achieved by avoiding any fibre coating, i.e. as-received carbon fibre structures can be used and are embedded in a carbonaceous polymer precursor without any additives. Furthermore, no reinfiltration steps are necessary and pyrolysis at 900° C as well as silicon infiltration at 1500° C are carried out each in a one-step process. The state of the art process is characterized by a manufacturing time of two weeks covering all three stages of the LSI process: CFRP near-net shaping, pyrolysis of the precursor and liquid silicon infiltration [1, 2].

Principally, the LSI process leads to C/C-SiC materials consisting of load carrying carbon fibres and matrices of carbon, silicon carbide and some free silicon. The constitution of the matrix and the material's microstructure mainly depend on the choice of matrix precursor and fibre structure, the processing parameters and the fibre/matrix interface. One main advantage

of the LSI process lies in the possibility to vary these parameters in a wide range leading to different qualities of C/C-SiC materials.

As for all composites the fibre/matrix bonding (FMB) has a dominating influence on fracture behaviour and physical properties. A common method to adapt the FMB in CMC materials in order to obtain a quasi-ductile fracture behaviour is the coating of carbon fibres prior to manufacturing. There exist different processes for fibre coatings but all of them are very expensive and no techniques are available to prepare woven fibre structures.

In case of C/C-SiC materials, the LSI process allows the modification of interfaces via a thermal treatment of carbon fibres. First investigations showed that these pretreatments can reduce the fibre/matrix bonding essentially in the polymer stage and therefore influence the formation of the microcrack pattern during pyrolysis [3, 4]. As a result, the microstructure and characteristics of the final ceramic stage show a wide variability, representing not only one single material but C/C-SiC products with quite different properties. These products are called SILCA as they are mainly based on silicon and carbon and all are manufactured by the same LSI process.

MATERIAL AND PROCESSING

All investigated C/C-SiC materials have been manufactured using the standard LSI process. That means CFRP shaping as well as pyrolysis and silicon infiltration have been conducted with identical processing parameters for each material. The variation was focused on the effects of different fibre/matrix bondings as a result of thermal fibre pretreatment. This pretreatment was carried out at different temperature levels in a nitrogen atmosphere.

The C/C-SiC material consists of bidirectionally woven fabrics of ex-PAN carbon fibres. High tenacity (HT) as well as intermediate modulus (IM) fibres from different manufacturers (Toray, Akzo) are used. The polymer precursor XP-60, a one-part thermosetting system, yields the carbon matrix after pyrolysis.

After the optional pretreatment the fabrics are embedded into the polymer by resin transfer moulding (RTM) and cured at 200° C for 8 hours. After curing, a void-free CRFP laminate exists with fibre volume contents of about 55 %. Plates of 300 x 300 x 3 mm³ were manufactured and characterized with samples in bending as well as tensile tests.

The subsequent pyrolysis, carried out at 900° C under nitrogen with the standard parameters, takes about 120 hours, including heating up and cooling down. A carbon matrix with an amorphous structure is formed by the pyrolysis of the polymer XP-60. The rearrangement of the molecular chains causes a volume shrinkage of about 60 %, combined with an increase in density to 1.8 g/cm³. The carbon yield of XP-60 is nearly independent of heating rate (Fig. 1), but low temperature gradients are worth striving for during pyrolysis. Depending on the fibre/matrix bonding forces, there are considerable stresses within the laminate due to the shrinkage of the matrix and the impediment of the fibre structure. To avoid delaminations or other imperfections the heating rate is limited to 3-5 K/h within the critical temperature range.

The volumetric shrinkage of the matrix is impeded anisotropically by the carbon fibres. While no macroscopical changes in geometry occur in the laminate's plane, the variation in laminate's thickness, i. e. perpendicular to the fibre orientation, depends on the FMB. During the conversion from polymer to carbon the matrix adopts a crack pattern which can be demonstrated by SEM micrographs and measured in terms of water absorption. Referring this value to the total volume, an open porosity can be defined which allows a characterization of the different microstructures.

Figure 1. Mass loss versus temperature of XP-60 depending on the heating rate

To form the silicon carbide matrix, liquid silicon is infiltrated at 1500° C. Due to the high purity and the low viscosity, the molten silicon is driven only by capillary forces into the porous microstructures. This infiltration is accompanied by the simultaneous chemical reaction

whereby the silicon preferable reacts with the amorphous structure of the carbon matrix.

The chemical reaction is controlled by a diffusion process and takes much more time than the infiltration process itself. The reaction time depends on the open porosity and morphology of the carbonaceous material after pyrolysis, and has to be optimized for each microstructure. In this work, all infiltration conditions, i. e. vacuum atmosphere at a constant temperature of 1500° C for about two hours, have been kept constant. As a consequence, there are three phases in the C/C-SiC material:

- β -silicon carbide
- carbon
- free silicon

The carbon is present in a crystalline modification within the fibres whereas an amorphous modification is present in the residual carbon matrix surrounding the fibres. In the case of non-stoichiometrical reactions between silicon and carbon matrix a certain amount of free silicon remains and is present as an intergranular phase between the SiC grains. This qualitative information can be observed by backscattered electron images of a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM).

TAILORING OF MICROSTRUCTURE

One requirement for good silicon infiltration is the formation of a translaminar crack pattern during pyrolysis. The morphology of this microcrack pattern is mainly influenced by the fibre/matrix bonding in the initial polymer stage.

Commercially available carbon fibres normally show a high amount of active surface groups to increase the adhesion within the polymer matrix. The use of as-received fabrics therefore leads to strong fibre/matrix bondings which can be measured in terms of interlaminar shear strength (ILSS). Typical values for composites based on XP-60 and fabric reinforcement lie in the range of 40-50 MPa.

During pyrolysis the matrix tends to contract isotropically in each direction impeded only by the fibre structure. In the direction parallel to the fibres the impediment reaches the highest values because of the macroscopical stability of the composite. With increasing pyrolysis temperature the contraction stresses locally exceed the tensile strength of the matrix resulting in a relaxation of the matrix by cracking. In case of high FMB this procedure repeats several times for each fibre bundle. As a result, segmentation of all bundles occur and lead to a translaminar crack pattern with dense C/C bundles consisting of about 300-500 individual fibres (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. C/C morphology after pyrolysis for high FMB

The infiltration of liquid silicon at 1500° C rapidly fills the cracks within some minutes. The dense matrix within the fibre bundles shields off the liquid silicon. Therefore, a layer of silicon carbide results around the bundles and only a small amount of carbon fibres are damaged. Fig. 3 shows a typical backscattered electron image of a fibre bundle where the SiC layers appear brighter than the carbon fibres and matrix, respectively.

Figure 3. Microstructure resulting from high FMB

Several pretreatments have been carried out at temperatures of up to 900° C. Fabric layers have been exposed to an inert atmosphere for up to two hours before using them as reinforcements. Typically, an interlaminar shear strength of 25-30 MPa is measured in the CFRP stage, indicating reduced bonding forces in the fibre/matrix interface. During pyrolysis these bondings are strong enough to form a crack pattern similar to that induced by high FMB. Nevertheless, additional cracks occur within the fibre bundles resulting in a higher open porosity of the C/C composite. As a result, liquid silicon is able to enter these spaces and reacts to form local SiC zones within the fibre bundles (Fig.4).

Figure 4. Microstructure resulting from reduced FMB

In comparison to high FMB the chemical attack of carbon fibres is more pronounced but the reduction of FMB also reduces the internal stress level within the bundles. As a consequence, these materials show an increased strength level as well as fracture toughness because of additional sliding surfaces within the bundles. A premature failure under loading can be avoided and energy dissipating effects result in an essential fibre pull-out after fracture.

By increasing the pretreatment temperature above 900° C the FMB decreases further and ILSS values for the CFRP composite are typically below 20 MPa. During pyrolysis these weak bondings lead to a shrinkage away of the matrix from the fibres. In contrast to the previous cases, no geometrical reduction in laminate's thickness occurs and the individual fibres remain in their original position. The C/C composite is totally microcracked, but not delaminated, resulting in a microstructure without any segmentation into fibre bundles. The internal stresses seem to be very low and each monofilament is only partially surrounded by carbon matrix.

During silicizing all cracks are filled by silicon, but the infiltration velocity is lower due to the high amount of porosity. Nevertheless, all composites could be infiltrated within the standard procedure. Much more silicon was absorbed by this microstructure, resulting in high densities of about 2.3 g/cm³. As there is no protection of the fibres, the liquid silicon reacts not only with the carbon matrix but also with the carbon fibres and leads to a more or less degradation of all monofilaments. This reduces the load carrying capability of the fibres essentially and the fracture behaviour becomes more similar to that of monolithic ceramics. Fig. 5 shows a typical microstructure of C/C-SiC resulting from low fibre/matrix bondings. The magnitude and sector of the image is identical to the microstructures of higher FMB shown in figure 3 and 4.

Figure 5. Microstructure resulting from low FMB

CHARACTERISTICS OF SILCA MATERIALS

As mentioned above, all C/C-SiC composites have been manufactured by the same LSI process and with the same precursor (XP-60). The only differences lie in the thermal preparation of the

carbon fabrics prior to manufacturing. Besides the morphological investigations, mechanical tests have been carried out with short beam samples (30 x 10 x 3 mm³), flexure samples (80 x 10 x 3 mm³) and tensile specimen (160 x 10 x 3 mm³) to evaluate the different pretreatments.

Principally, all investigated SILCA materials can be divided according to their properties into three different groups. Untreated carbon fibres lead to high FMB with moderate mechanical strength and strain values and a quite brittle fracture behaviour. This material of so-called XB-quality shows flexural and tensile strength values of 160 and 80 MPa, respectively. These values are constant up to 1600° C combined with an excellent thermoshock stability.

Considerable higher strength values are obtained by an improved fibre/matrix interface. The fracture behaviour shows a more pronounced quasi-ductility resulting from pull-out effects of fibres prior to failure. These materials can be summarized in another group, showing a mean flexure strength of 300 MPa and a strain to failure of 0.35 %. At the moment, these C/C-SiC materials represent the highest quality of the LSI process and are abbreviated by XT.

More densified materials with densities of 2.3 g/cm³ and an open porosity lower than 1 % are the result of low FMB. The strength values are comparably low but the stiffness is nearly twice of the XB and XT quality. Therefore, these materials seem to be more suited for components with very limited deformation tolerances under moderate load, e. g. in mirrors or optical benches. However, the residual amount of free silicon restricts these XD-materials to application temperatures below the silicon melting point of 1420° C. Table 1 summarizes the mechanical properties of the three SILCA qualities.

Table 1. SILCA qualities and their properties

Material Quality	XB	XT	XD
Flexural Strength [MPa]	160	300	80
Tensile Strength [MPa]	80	190	30
Strain [%]	0.15	0.35	0.04
Young's Modulus [GPa]	60	60	100
Density [10 ³ kg/m ³]	1.9	1.9	2.3
Open Porosity [%]	3.5	3.5	1.0

APPLICATIONS

C/C-SiC materials are suitable for many application fields where high thermal and chemical stability is required. Their low density combined with their excellent thermoshock resistance predestines them as light weight materials in aerospace structures. Very complex C/C-SiC structures have already been realized and demonstrate the transferability of the material's characteristics from small samples to real components [5].

At the moment SILCA qualities are in different stages of development. Most experiences and a very good reproducibility have been achieved with XB materials. Besides their good thermomechanical properties first investigations have shown their excellent ablative and oxidative stability under friction and wear conditions. High coefficients of friction of up to 1.0 lead to the development of C/C-SiC brake discs for high performance brake systems. A set of two stators and one rotor has been manufactured (Fig. 6). The discs were originally made as square plates and subsequently machined to the final disc shape by erosion techniques. The discs show a thickness of about 13 mm and an outer diameter of 280 mm with a mass of less than 1.5 kg. First tests have been successful and demonstrate the high potential of C/C-SiC as braking materials [6].

Figure 6. Prototypes of C/C-SiC Brake Discs

The LSI process allows a wide variability of component's shape and size. Figure 7 shows some basic elements made of SILCA in XB and XT quality as developed within national research programmes. Using traditional CFRP technologies there are nearly no restrictions in geometry apart from the availability of a vacuum furnace with sufficient size. Today the DLR's laboratory furnace allows the manufacturing of profiles with a maximum length of 0.5 m. With tube sized furnaces much longer profiles in the range of several meters would be principally feasible, allowing an efficient production of tubes, e. g. for a new generation of heat exchangers.

Figure 7. Basic elements of C/C-SiC materials

CONCLUSIONS

The LSI process has been developed as an alternative technology to produce CMC structural components. It is based on the liquid silicon infiltration into porous carbon fibre structures resulting in C/C-SiC materials with high thermal and corrosive stability. By different thermal pretreatments of the reinforcing carbon fibres the microstructure was tailored to the infiltration dynamics of liquid silicon.

Three qualities of SILCA materials have been manufactured, based on the same raw material and processing parameters. Each of them represents different properties and application fields showing the variability of the LSI process. Complex and highly integrated structural components have been realized as demonstrators and were tested successfully. As no expensive fibre coatings are necessary, the LSI process offers the potential of cost-effective manufacture of CMC due to short manufacturing times and low raw material costs.

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